

The future of online education: motivation, personalization and interaction on the Campster learning management system

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Abstract

Massive open online courses promised great results in the 2010s, but fundamental flaws in the conception and design of online education technologies have rendered them time-consuming and ineffective, leading to student disengagement and low course completion rates. The COVID-19 pandemic, climate crisis, rapid automation and shifts in the labor market are creating a pressing demand for scalable and effective education technologies. The paper discusses the limitations of existing education technology design and proposes solutions based on both current scientific literature and user data from the Campster online learning platform.

Background

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a transformative effect on online education, bringing to light both the indispensability of this technology, and the many limitations it must overcome to become a viable option for the future. The Campster learning management system was created in 2017 with the goal of developing a solution to those shortcomings of online education technology (EdTech) design that lead to decreased learner motivation and engagement, resulting in dramatically low course completion rates.

As Campster co-founder and research lead, my goal was to design a user-centric educational technology which would fundamentally transform the experience of learning as a difficult and unpleasant activity, to one which is fulfilling, engaging and part of everyday life. In doing so, we were guided by the insight that motivation is more important for learning results than information. Today Campster operates in six countries (Serbia, Croatia, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Romania and Ukraine), serving over 550,000 users who are taking courses in numerous subjects from languages, to programming, personal development, business and others, based on Campster's proprietary software, learning methodology and content.

When Campster was founded in 2017, e-learning had the reputation of a mature industry with limited potential for growth and innovation. From great expectations that MOOCs (massive open online courses) would replace face-to-face teaching, it had emerged that e-learning was in many ways ineffective and time-consuming. There is a telling statistic that was widely shared at the time and which remains relevant today: out of every 100 people who enroll in a MOOC, only 12.6 go on to complete it, on average (Jordan 2015). Critics point to the fact that not all those who register for a course aim to even browse it, much less complete it, but even when we take into account student intention, only 22% of those who intended to complete a MOOC actually do

so (Reich 2014). This poses an issue not only for users, but also for businesses, and it is a challenge that Campster has targeted from its outset. Campster has achieved great success in increasing course completion rates up to three-fold with strategic and research-based interaction and engagement functionalities, as well as UX design, as I will show in the latter part of this article. We continue to work towards improving that even further with the development of an adaptive learning system, which I will discuss in more detail.

Nevertheless, low course completion rates have been a long-standing standard and as recently as just two years ago, the problem was receiving surprisingly little attention outside of academic circles. Great changes in society, business and technology, however, occur when unexpected events spark innovation. The COVID-19 pandemic was one such event that accelerated the global expansion and adoption of online education which had seemingly overnight become indispensable (Govindarajan and Srivastava 2020). At the same time, it has also become a source of many challenges and frustrations to educators, learners and parents worldwide, demonstrating both the great potential of the EdTech industry as well as how ripe it is for innovation and disruption (Gallagher and Palmer 2020). In fact, as investment intelligence firm HolonIQ points out (2020), “the first half of 2020 was the second largest half-year for Global EdTech Venture Capital”. The expectations are that over \$87bn will be invested in EdTech over the next 10 years, which is almost three times more than in the previous decade (ibid.).

What does the future of online education have in store? Can online education technology fulfill its initial promise and become a tool which supports students, teachers and facilitates learning processes rather than impeding them? What improvements are required to make IT infrastructure more suitable for online education? These are the questions that I will discuss below on the basis of three key insights identified both in academic literature and in the long-term analysis of the learning behavior of more than three hundred thousand Campster users.

Motivation as the core learning success factor - What we learn with pleasure, we never forget

Formal, face-to-face learning environments have undergone a great transformation in the last decade towards more student-centric, active and collaborative learning models. At the same time, online education still lags behind due to the limitations posed by technology design. Research has shown that active and collaborative learning not only increases student retention rates, but also encourages deep learning (Deslauriers et al. 2019, Freeman et al. 2014, Prince 2004). In order to implement an active classroom, one must adopt new instruction models and strategies, but also change the very design of the classroom, that is, the space in which learning takes place. This transformation has been in the works both globally and in Serbia in the last decade and with promising results.

On the other hand, if we take a look at online education today, it is dominated by the more traditional, teacher-centric instruction model in which knowledge is transferred in one direction, from teacher to students who act as passive recipients of knowledge. Due to the convenience and cost-effectiveness of asynchronous online classes students often do not have the opportunity to engage with a teacher or peers in any way, but can do so only with a pdf or a pre-recorded video. Most users of online courses in Serbia have reported feeling isolated, unengaged and unmotivated as a result, according to a study conducted by IPSOS (2021) on a nationally representative sample. As a consequence, they need more effort to follow and understand the subject matter in an online setting, which, as we have seen, in the majority of cases leads to high drop out rates.

In order to turn that around, in developing the Campster online learning platform we have modeled the recent transformation of face-to-face teaching which has shown that we must not only adopt new instruction and learning models, but also change the very space - the learning environment, in which instruction and learning are taking place. Campster is therefore based on four key principles:

- **Learning in a community** - Learning happens through interaction (with the system, the content, the peers and mentors) by applying the network effect,
- **Learning as a feeling of success** - The platform is designed with the goal to motivate and retain users, and support them in finishing what they started.
- **Gamification** - Applicable to all subject areas, with special features for language learning.
- **Accessibility** - Scalable technology keeps prices accessible, as does offering course content in users' native language. Over 70% of users prefer learning in their native language as opposed to learning in English, as the IPSOS study has shown (2021).

As a result, Campster has been designed as an ecosystem within which a user can participate in multiple types of synchronous and asynchronous didactic activities and make diverse connections to different elements and participants. These activities are all linked according to predefined relations and hierarchies into one complex system, and the goal of the platform is to encourage users to spend as much time as possible using it - whether they are accessing course content, doing quizzes or other assessments, chatting with peers as they play games, or helping others and participating in knowledge exchange. Within the Campster learning ecosystem, all of these activities and many more are considered part of the user's learning experience and all of these positively contribute to an increase in motivation and as a result, to better learning outcomes.

Therefore, even though there is often an emphasis on trends and complex solutions, when it comes to education some things never change: we must put motivation in the center of any instruction model for learning to be effective.

Social learning - Who do we turn to when we wish to learn something new?

According to Degreed and the Harvard Business Review, when employees want to learn something new 62% will turn to their professional network, 45% will ask their supervisor or mentor, and 44% will seek out the help of their colleagues. This is a positive practice which should be encouraged more, given that research has shown the significance of questioning as a learning strategy (Chin & Osborne 2008). As Graesser and Olde (2003) have demonstrated, students ask questions when there is a discrepancy in the learning process and this leads to better understanding, but also drives critical thinking and factual recall (Ennis 1993). Companies which encourage learning among their employees are more successful, and students studying in supportive environments where peers feel safe to ask and exchange knowledge with each other achieve better results on the whole.

Campster results also align with the above. In 2017, once we had developed the beta version of the Campster platform, we ran a test to confirm our hypotheses on online learning environment design. We compared the results of two representative groups of Serbian secondary school students taking an identical 3-month program consisting of two courses: Introduction to programming (introductory level course) and Web Development (advanced level course). The first group took the courses on the Moodle platform and with the help of a live instructor who was available for any questions and support. The second took the same courses on the test version of the Campster platform which was designed to harness the network effect through gamified user interaction, and with minimal involvement of an instructor whose role was primarily that of a moderator. The results are shown in the graphs below:

Effect of Campster LMS on course completion rates

Figure 1. Effect of Campster LMS on course completion rates.

Effect of Campster LMS on moderator costs

Figure 2. Effect of Campster LMS on moderator costs.

We have observed that when the learning process is designed to encourage social interaction, students are transformed from passive recipients of knowledge into active participants and collaborators. Students feel “seen” and that their presence and contribution are important, which creates a form of positive peer pressure that is extremely motivating. This factor becomes even more important in an online setting, when students are alone in front of their screens. The gamification of interaction adds an additional level of encouragement and incentive.

Adaptive learning systems - Not too difficult, not too easy, but just right!

One of the main challenges of face-to-face teaching is that the instructor has limited time to dedicate to each individual student. The pace of the group will usually adjust to the median student, leading to missed opportunities to help each individual fulfill their potential. When faced with a task that is either too challenging or too easy, when they are too far ahead or fall too far behind their peers, learners disengage. The difficulty of the task must be just right for optimal learning results and here lies the greatest potential of education technologies.

With support from the Innovation Fund of the Republic of Serbia, we are currently developing the Campster AI tutor app, an adaptive learning technology which adjusts the learning path to each individual user and identifies their strong and weak points. In order to develop the most effective system and differentiate between functionalities which appear attractive from those that actually support user goals, we are applying evidence-based decision making (see Schildkamp 2012 for an overview).

As discussed above, one of the main challenges of online learning are high drop-out rates. It is crucial for learning technology to support retention and lead the user towards course completion. In order to achieve that, the Campster system monitors and registers all those different moments in user experience that create friction, uncovering the two major moments when users permanently leave a course. The number one reason users never complete a course they signed up for is that they never actually start the course. This aligns with other research on the topic, as outlined by Reich and Ruiperez-Valiente (2019). The second biggest reason they give up is because the material is too easy or too difficult: the difficulty of the program needs to be just right for optimal learning outcomes.

The adaptive AI tutor app will aim to rectify both issues by redesigning the learning experience to include the following key processes, among others:

- implement seamless progress from enrollment onto the learning journey with **Personalized and interactive onboarding**,
- design personalized learning journeys for each user to keep them motivated and challenged enough with the **Adaptive content engine**, and
- increase interaction, engagement and learning results through the **Adaptive Game Engine**.

As a consequence, each user will create a personalized learning journey and at any time encounter learning challenges that are just difficult and achievable enough to keep them motivated. In addition, by continually tracking data and optimizing the learning experience, the adaptive AI tutor app will further support learners towards course completion.

Conclusion

From the start of the COVID-19 pandemic, we have been faced with the question of whether technology can replace great teachers. Experience tells us that it cannot and should not - live contact, the energy and connections it brings are irreplaceable. However, as we have seen in the last two years, online education can be an indispensable tool in the hands of great teachers. Due to increased automation and rapid changes on the labor market, 54% of the workforce will require significant upskilling and reskilling within the next five years (World Economic Forum 2018), creating a pressing need for high-quality, on-demand scalable education.

Only online education technology has the potential to adequately respond to a demand of such magnitude and provide training to all those that require it, even if they work and live in remote locations far away from the centers of knowledge. However, as the results above demonstrate, edtech can live up to this promise only if it is designed with the needs of the human learner in mind, facilitating social and active learning and if it successfully implements its most promising draw - adaptive learning.

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Budućnost online obrazovanja: motivacija, personalizacija i interakcija na Kampster sistemu za upravljanje učenjem

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Sažetak

Masovni otvoreni online kursevi obećavali su sjajne rezultate u 2010-oj, ali temeljni nedostaci u koncepciji i dizajnu tehnologije online obrazovanja učinili su ih dugotrajnim i neučinkovitim, što je dovelo do neangažovanja studenata i niske stope završetka kurseva. Pandemija COVID-19, klimatska kriza, brza automatizacija i promene na tržištu rada stvarile su hitnu potražnju za skalabilnim i učinkovitim obrazovnim tehnologijama. U ovom radu se ističu ključna ograničenja postojećeg dizajna obrazovne tehnologije i predlažu rešenja utemeljena na aktualnoj literaturi i korisničkim podacima sa Kampster platforme za online učenje.